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an Atlantaigh

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From Research to Impact:

ATU Research-Informed, Industry-Linked
Policy Brief Series

Academic Year 2025/2026

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an Atlantaigh

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ATU Research-Informed, Industry-Linked Policy Brief Series

This publication was compiled by the ATU Research Coordinator Team under the RISE@ATU programme, with editorial coordination, design and booklet preparation undertaken by Dr Shane Conway.

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What is a Policy Brief?

Policy briefs are concise, accessible, outward-facing summaries of research evidence designed to inform policymakers, industry stakeholders, practitioners and wider society. Unlike traditional academic publications, policy briefs translate peer-reviewed research into clear insights, recommendations and practical implications for non-specialist audiences.

The ATU Research-Informed, Industry-Linked Policy Brief Series supports knowledge mobilisation by enhancing the visibility, accessibility and societal relevance of research conducted across Atlantic Technological University, aligned with regional, national and international priorities.

May 2026

The views expressed within this Policy Brief Series are based on independent, peer-reviewed research and do not necessarily reflect the position of RISE@ATU.

RISE@ATU is co-funded by the Government of Ireland and the European Union through the ERDF Northern & Western Regional Programme 2021-2027

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Atlantic Technological University (ATU) is pleased to present the inaugural compilation of the ATU Research-Informed, Industry-Linked Policy Brief Series for the academic year 2025/2026, a university-wide initiative initiated and developed by the Research Coordinator Team under [RISE@ATU](#).

This series emerged directly from the findings of the ATU Researcher Engagement Campaign (2025), a bottom-up consultation undertaken by the ATU Research Coordinator Team involving over 25% of ATU's research-active community across all nine campuses. The campaign highlighted the need for stronger institutional mechanisms to support research visibility, recognition, interdisciplinary awareness and the communication of academic knowledge in formats accessible beyond traditional scholarly audiences. In response, the ATU Policy Brief Series was established as a structured platform for translating peer-reviewed research into concise, outward-facing summaries aimed at policymakers, industry partners, practitioners and community stakeholders. Published monthly through [Zenodo](#), the European Commission-supported open research repository, each brief is assigned a unique DOI, providing researchers with formal recognition, measurable visibility and enhanced dissemination opportunities.

The series reflects a growing international and European emphasis on research impact, knowledge mobilisation and evidence-informed policymaking. This is increasingly reflected in initiatives led by the [European Research Executive Agency \(REA\)](#), including the development of practical guidance to support the communication, dissemination and exploitation of scientific results for policymakers, industry stakeholders and wider society. It also aligns with the [Government of Ireland's Three Pillars of Policy Development](#) framework, which emphasises the integration of evidence, implementation and legitimacy in policymaking. In an increasingly complex and rapidly changing world, publicly funded research is now expected not only to generate knowledge, but also to contribute meaningfully to societal, economic and policy development through effective communication and stakeholder engagement.

The policy briefs included within this booklet, synthesising peer-reviewed journal articles, span all four ATU faculties and represent the breadth, interdisciplinarity and societal relevance of research taking place across the university. Collectively, they showcase the diversity of expertise and applied research activity emerging across ATU, covering topics such as sustainability, tourism, digital transformation, health, sport and exercise science, agri-food innovation, entrepreneurship, creative industries, engineering, artificial intelligence, education, and community wellbeing. The series also demonstrates strong alignment with the seven sectoral strengths and potential opportunities for the North-West Region outlined in [Ireland's Smart Specialisation Strategy \(S3\)](#), while contributing to several [United Nations Sustainable Development Goals \(SDGs\)](#), including health and wellbeing, sustainable communities, quality education, responsible consumption, climate action, innovation, and reduced inequalities.

Importantly, this initiative has also been driven by the strong engagement and enthusiasm of the ATU research community, including research staff and PhD researchers. Since its launch in December 2025, the series has resulted in the publication of 23 policy briefs, highlighting a clear appetite across faculties and campuses for accessible, impactful and publicly engaged research communication.

The ATU Research Coordinator Team would like to sincerely thank all contributing authors for their willingness to engage with this initiative and for their continued commitment to ensuring that ATU research reaches audiences beyond academia. We hope this compilation serves not only as a showcase of the quality and diversity of research taking place across ATU, but also as a reflection of the university's growing emphasis on research impact, external engagement and knowledge mobilisation in practice.

Dr Shane Conway, Editorial Coordinator, ATU Policy Brief Series

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Tourism Enterprise Climate Action Literacy: Emissions Measurement, Monitoring & Reporting

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

This study evaluates climate action literacy among tourism enterprises and their efforts to measure, monitor, and report emissions. Integrating climate action into tourism policies is vital for sustainable development and aligns with the EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (2022), requiring environmental and social reporting by 2028. Using UN, UNWTO, and SDG frameworks, the study identifies gaps between theory and practice. Achieving Net-Zero demands a skilled, climate-literate workforce capable of implementing decarbonisation strategies. Policymakers should prioritise training, standardised reporting, and workforce development to strengthen tourism's climate contribution. Building enterprise capacity will ensure transparency, compliance, and long-term progress toward sustainable, low-carbon tourism.

Research Findings

Findings show major gaps in tourism enterprises' climate action and Net-Zero readiness. While most know 2030 goals, awareness of 2050 decarbonisation targets is limited. Terms like "decarbonisation" and "Net-Zero destination" are poorly understood, leading to weak implementation. Only 14% measure emissions, mostly via consultants, with little focus on indirect (Scope 2–3) emissions. This lack of capacity and transparency hinders progress and risks EU compliance. Policymakers must promote clear terminology, training, and reskilling to improve measurement and reporting. Strengthening literacy, embedding decarbonisation, and fostering collaboration are vital to align tourism with Net-Zero and the UN SDGs.

Policy Implications

Sustainable tourism depends on monitoring of environmental performance, with enterprises playing a key role by measuring and reporting emissions to track decarbonisation progress. However, while this study's small sample size limits representativeness and its focus on one destination reduces global applicability, it does offer early insights into climate action literacy that can guide wider sectoral learning. The lack of longitudinal tracking restricts understanding of progress in climate literacy and decarbonisation. External factors such as market, economic, and regulatory conditions were not considered, though they affect climate action adoption. Policymakers should prioritise standardised reporting frameworks, targeted training and consistent guidance, while systemic changes are needed to support capacity building, enable transparent data collection and encourage sustained climate action across the sector.

Industry Recommendations

To enable tourism's transition to Net-Zero by 2050, urgent action is required to reskill and upskill the workforce for a decarbonised future. While enterprises demonstrate climate action literacy and acknowledge their role in emission reduction, significant gaps remain in implementation and long-term preparedness. Under EU law, all enterprises must report sustainability impacts by 2028, making workforce training in emission measurement, monitoring, and reporting essential. Policymakers should promote standardised frameworks, international collaboration, and longitudinal research to assess progress and address regional challenges. Future policies must integrate economic, regulatory, and environmental factors to encourage industry-wide participation and transparency. Strengthening capacity, aligning with the UN Sustainable Development Goals, and fostering evidence-based practices will ensure tourism contributes effectively to global climate action and sustainable development goals.

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Further Reading:

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Tourism Enterprise's Level of
Climate Action Literacy and
Measuring, Monitoring and
Reporting of Emissions, Tourism:
An International Interdisciplinary
Journal, 7(2), 367-380 DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.37741/t.73.2.14>

National Smart Specialisation

Strategy (S3) Theme: Renewable
Energy, Climate Change Mitigation
& Sustainability

Sustainable Development Goal

(SDG): SDG 13: Climate Action

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A Study of Literary Festivals in Ireland from a Management Perspective

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Literary festivals are important drivers of literary tourism, connecting readers, authors and cultural stakeholders while supporting regional cultural development. Despite their significance, they remain underexplored within festival and event management research, which has largely focused on audience dynamics rather than organisational practices. This study addresses that gap by examining literary festivals in Ireland through a management lens, with attention to governance, planning, business models and marketing. Using qualitative and quantitative methods, it aims to understand how these festivals evolve and operate, and how management practices influence their sustainability, cultural value and contribution to tourism and destination development.

Research Findings

The study identifies key components required for effective literary festival management, highlighting the importance of balancing artistic vision, operational delivery, financial sustainability, and community engagement. Successful festivals demonstrate strong strategic planning, expert programming, and innovative festivalscape design. They also require robust governance structures that enhance transparency and accountability, along with diversified funding models to ensure financial resilience. Innovative communication approaches and immersive audience engagement strategies help festivals broaden their reach and improve attendee experience. Together, these findings provide a clearer understanding of how Irish literary festivals function within the wider cultural and tourism ecosystem.

Policy Implications

Literary festivals contribute significantly to cultural development, tourism, and regional identity, but their long-term sustainability depends on targeted policy support. Policymakers should prioritise multi-annual funding structures, capacity-building initiatives and professional development pathways that recognise festivals' evolving organisational needs. Strengthening partnerships between local authorities, arts agencies, tourism bodies and festival organisers would enhance resource sharing and regional impact. Policies that support volunteer development, cultural programming and destination marketing can further strengthen festival resilience. Understanding festivals' economic, cultural, and social benefits provides a compelling rationale for ongoing investment to ensure these events continue enriching communities and supporting Ireland's cultural landscape.

Industry Recommendations

Festival organisers should adopt structured management frameworks that support sustainable operations, financial resilience and strong community relationships. A typology of festival models, a collaborative business framework, and a stakeholder engagement model can guide organisers in refining governance, revenue diversification and volunteer coordination. The study's integrated ten-step management framework provides a practical blueprint for planning, delivering, and marketing festivals effectively. By implementing these approaches, organisers can improve decision-making, strengthen accountability, enhance cultural programming and increase audience engagement. These strategies support resilience, long-term viability, and meaningful cultural and tourism impacts within Ireland's festival landscape.

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Further Reading:

McGuckin, M., Linehan, M. &
Leahy, R. (2025) Narratives and
Networks: Managing Ireland's
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**National Smart Specialisation
Strategy (S3) Theme:** Audio
Visual/Creative

**Sustainable Development Goal
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and Communities

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

Exploring Top Management Support for Digital Transformation: A Case Study of a European Financial Services Organisation

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Digital transformation (DT) offers many opportunities for value creation, customer personalisation, and efficiency, yet over 70–90% of initiatives fail due to cultural resistance, fragmented legacy systems, and poor leadership alignment. Traditional organisations struggle when DT is framed as an IT upgrade rather than a business-wide transformation. This study investigates how top management at a leading European bank supported a successful DT. The objective was to provide empirical insight into top management (TM) actions, an area the literature describes as underexplored and surprisingly neglected. This research aims to clarify how leadership behaviours, strategic alignment and cultural interventions influence DT outcomes.

Research Findings

This study identifies four interconnected TM actions critical to successful DT: Reimagining the organisation's strategic direction, Reconfiguring culture and workforce practices, Recalibrating capabilities and systems, and Reinventing customer value propositions. To support a successful DT, TM expanded the scope from technology replacement to include strategy, culture, and business model renewal, supported by structural changes to the TM team and cultural transformation initiatives focused on communication, reducing silos, and fostering collaboration, to create a more digitally agile workforce. TM also pursued IS integration, insourcing digital talent, and customer-facing innovations, including new data-driven services.

Policy Implications

Policy frameworks should encourage organisations, especially in regulated industries, to adopt holistic digital strategies that integrate DT with cultural and workforce transformation, echoing the study's finding that technology alone cannot deliver DT benefits. Policies should also emphasise leadership capability, long-term investment and workforce readiness. Regulators and government agencies should support integrated digital strategies rather than isolated technology upgrades. Public programmes should promote digital skills, organisational agility and cross-sector collaboration, ensuring organisations can modernise safely while protecting consumers and maintaining service quality.

Industry Recommendations

Industry leaders should view DT as a whole-business change rather than just an IT implementation project. TM teams need shared ownership, transparent communication, and a clear digital vision. TM must also ensure that the right people are involved to capture all perspectives during a DT and should engage and empower their workforce in preparation for the future organisations. Organisations should invest in modern digital platforms, develop internal talent, streamline processes, and redesign structures to enable quicker decision-making. Customer-focused innovation, data-driven insights, and partnerships within the digital ecosystem are vital for sustainable digital competitiveness. TM must also remember that digital technology is merely an enabler of change; it will not transform.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

ICT & ICT Services

**Sustainable Development Goal
(SDG):** SDG 8: Decent Work and
Economic Growth

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

Mapping The Consumer Journey in the Hotel Industry: Guest Segmentation and Experience Evolution

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Accommodation experiences are multifaceted. Consumer journey mapping research generally focuses on the purchase decision or post-consumption stage in isolation. This does not adequately reflect the nature of continuous interactions in the hospitality industry. This study sought to provide a holistic analysis of the consumer journey in the luxury hotel industry. Specifically we sought to identify critical touchpoints that influence satisfaction and loyalty by analysing the entire consumer journey; to segment guests according to their satisfaction levels to understand different profiles and behaviour patterns; and to provide a comprehensive perspective on customer experience management by integrating emotional and rational factors.

Research Findings

K-means clustering identified three guest delight segments: 'Dissatisfied Seekers', 'Content but Cautious' and 'Delighted Advocates'. Results highlight differing decision-making factors, experiences and emotions encountered at various stages of the customer journey by each segment, indicating the need to develop tailored service delivery strategies. Consistent service and proactive recovery are essential to improve the experiences of 'Dissatisfied Seekers'. Consistent service, personalised touches and loyalty offers will help convert 'Content but Cautious' consumers into loyal advocates. Delighted advocates value personalised, emotionally resonant experiences that foster repeat visits and word-of-mouth. Ongoing innovation and tailored enhancements will help maintain their loyalty.

Policy Implications

The tourism sector, including luxury accommodation, is one of Ireland's largest employment sectors. Luxury hotels can act as an anchor business in regions, stimulating spending in the locality. Policymakers should prioritise subsidising professional development programmes that upskill hospitality staff in empathy and emotional engagement. Policies that support shared systems or collaborative frameworks to analyse post stay evaluations to inform policy and sector-wide benchmarking are valuable. Research grants to enable the exploration of the holistic consumer journey, tracking consumer delight over time, across stays in all hotel categories, will facilitate the development of policies that reinforce Ireland's global hospitality brand.

Industry Recommendations

'Dissatisfied Seekers' value proactive recovery and real-time feedback. Staff should identify early signs of dissatisfaction and respond empathetically. Tools including in-room surveys enable quick resolution. Acknowledging feedback and outlining improvements in post-stay follow ups rebuilds trust and fosters positive word-of-mouth. 'Content but Cautious' guests value consistency. Clear pre-arrival communication and personalised offers enhance perceived value. Loyalty programs and exclusive incentives drive repeat bookings. 'Delighted Advocates' should receive tailored benefits, unique experiences, and advocacy programs. Personalised welcomes and unique experiences reinforce their status, while public recognition further strengthens loyalty, turning them into brand ambassadors.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Audio-visual / Creative

Sustainable Development Goal

(SDG): SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

How Do Older People Experience Person-Centred Integrated Care? An Integrative Review of the Evidence

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

'Person-centred integrated care' (PCIC) has emerged in literature, policy and practice to meet the increasing care needs of an older population living longer with increased levels of chronic illness, multimorbidity and at enhanced risk of care fragmentation. Most evaluations of PCIC have been service-centred, rather than person-centred, and there is a lack of research on the effects of integrated care on patients, especially older people. This integrative review sought to identify and synthesise available evidence on older people's PCIC experiences, asking what empirical literature was available on the PCIC experiences of older people. Specifically, the objectives were: i) to ascertain how empirical literature defines integrated care and conceptualises person-centredness in the context of integrated care; ii) to explore how PCIC impacts on older people's care experiences; iii) to identify the main components of older people's positive PCIC experiences; and iv) to identify the barriers to the successful provision of PCIC for older people.

Research Findings

Findings included: i) definitions and components of integrated care and conceptualisations of person-centredness in the context of integrated care; ii) older people's positive PCIC experiences featured: coordination; continuity and relational care; involvement in care, including effective communication and information about care; and holistic care; iii) integrated care optimises care when successfully delivered, however, older people's experiences were mixed; and iv) barriers included a lack of integrated care frameworks developed from patients' perspectives, poor communication and information and staff shortages and turnover leading to discontinuity, limited time for meaningful interactions and follow-up care.

Policy Implications

Studies highlighted PCIC, as opposed to disease-specific and service-centred integrated care, as crucial for older people living with multiple and complex conditions to avoid fragmentation and cater for diverse and complex needs, leading to higher satisfaction with care and feelings of respect and equality.

While PCIC optimises care experiences, its evaluation is challenged by multiple conceptualisations and lack of engagement with service users.

Industry Recommendations

Integrated care models and framework must incorporate patient and carer perspectives into service design and evaluation. Implications for service design include the importance of prioritising experiences of continuity and coordination, relational care and holistic assessment and ensuring sufficient time for meaningful communication and interactions between older people, carers and staff.

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Further Reading:

Murphy, S., McCance, T. & White, P.J. (2025) How Do Older People Experience Person-Centred Integrated Care? An Integrative Review of the Evidence, *International Journal of Integrated Care*, 25(4), 1-21. **DOI:** <https://doi.org/10.5334/ijic.9066>

National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): SDG 3: Good Health & Wellbeing

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Beyond the Checklist: Are Gaelic Games' Concussion Protocols Supporting Psychological Recovery

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Concussion (or mild traumatic brain injury) is a frequent but often poorly managed injury in Gaelic games. Current return-to-play approaches focus mainly on physical symptoms, while psychological recovery such as anxiety, fear of re-injury, and social isolation are rarely addressed. Inconsistent and poorly enforced protocols combined with uneven concussion education across clubs and counties further increase risks to player welfare. The objectives of this research are to highlight gaps in current concussion management, emphasise the importance of psychological recovery, and support the development of consistent, enforceable, and player-centred concussion policies across all levels of Gaelic games.

Research Findings

Qualitative data from Gaelic games athletes indicates that concussion recovery is often poorly structured and inconsistently applied. Psychological effects such as anxiety, low mood, fear of re-injury, and loss of sporting identity were commonly reported, yet rarely addressed in formal recovery processes. Athletes described pressure to return to play, limited access to specialist support, and confusion around recovery timelines. Concussion education was variable, and many players only recognised the seriousness of concussion after experiencing it themselves. Overall, current practices prioritise physical clearance while neglecting mental and emotional recovery.

Policy Implications

Policymakers should recognise concussion (or mild traumatic brain injury) as a whole-person injury requiring both physical and psychological management. There is a clear need for visible, enforceable return to play protocols which apply consistently across all Gaelic sports and playing levels. Psychological screening and support should be embedded within concussion pathways. Regular and mandatory education for coaches, referees, medical staff, and players is required to improve recognition, reduce stigma, and prevent premature return to play. Clear governance and accountability mechanisms are essential to ensure protocols are followed in practice, not just in policy.

Industry Recommendations

The Gaelic Games Association (GAA) should promote a single, standardised concussion return to play framework which includes psychological recovery checkpoints. Sideline decision-making should be supported by objective assessment tools, reducing pressure on players to self-report or minimise the injury. Teams (club and intercounty) should be supported with access to trained personnel and clear referral pathways for psychological support. Regular education programmes should be delivered across all levels of Gaelic games. These measures would enhance player welfare, reduce long-term health risks, and strengthen confidence in concussion management systems in the GAA.

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Further Reading:

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/17479541241289983>

National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): SDG 3: Good Health & Wellbeing

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Time to Say Goodbye? Exploring the Entrepreneurial Transition to Retirement

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Most entrepreneurs will plan for retirement, and in the end, most will decide to retire. However, there are a complex range of push and pull factors which influence both the willingness and ability of our entrepreneurs to retire. This study presents the experiences of entrepreneurs who are approaching the end of their careers and what society defines as working life. This topic is a significant gap in the literature and existing terms used to describe retirement do not accurately capture the retirement considerations of entrepreneurs.

Research Findings

This study draws on a series of two interviews conducted with 15 entrepreneurs who are approaching what is commonly defined as the end of working life. To frame the findings, the interview data are consolidated into four distinct narrative types that reflect different approaches to retirement. The naming of these types draws on musical references, paying homage to Queen, Earth Wind and Fire, Justin Bieber and Dusty Springfield, which serve to make them memorable while also offering a light cultural touchpoint. The descriptions of each type are intended to resonate with both the study's readership and the entrepreneurs themselves.

Policy Implications

What is significant is that there is very limited evidence that individuals who pursue a long-term entrepreneurial career will have a strong desire to retire. The value of this research is that it is the first of its kind to create a typology of entrepreneurial retirement typologies providing novel insights for both future research and public policy design. Researchers must understand the entrepreneurial career in order to project forward the levels, pace and timing of entrepreneurial retirement. The insights from this study contribute to the literature on entrepreneurial careers, specifically by unpacking the end of career trajectories of older entrepreneurs.

Industry Recommendations

We should engage with the entrepreneurs in their networks. Talk to them about their plans for retirement. Ask them to make plans, ask them to consider how best to manage the end of working life for them, their families, their staff and their communities. The transition to retirement is a seismic event for our entrepreneurs and needs careful and consider planning on a par with that associated with starting an entrepreneurial journey.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme: Renewable Energy, Climate Change & Sustainability

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): SDG 3: Good Health & Wellbeing

The content and views included in this policy brief are based on independent, peer-reviewed research and do not necessarily reflect the position of RISE@ATU.

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Different Realities After Cancer: Why Personalised Support Matters for Quality of Life

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Cancer and its treatments often leave lasting impacts on individual's physical, emotional, and social wellbeing. While overall survival rates have improved, many individuals report ongoing challenges that affect daily life long after diagnosis and treatment. This study aimed to better understand how quality of life varies among people living with and beyond cancer by identifying distinct patterns of experiences and needs. Using a data-driven approach, we explored how health-related quality of life clusters into groups and examined factors associated with these patterns, to inform more personalised healthcare and support strategies.

Research Findings

This study identified three distinct health-related quality of life (HRQoL) profiles among those living with and beyond cancer using a person-centred latent profile analysis approach. These profiles; high wellbeing, compromised wellbeing, and low wellbeing; highlight substantial differences in individual experiences that is not captured by average HRQoL scores alone. Physical strength was linked with better quality of life, while more nutrition related symptoms and working were associated with poorer outcomes. Participants generally reported more symptoms and lower functioning than the general population, highlighting the ongoing challenges faced by those affected by cancer.

Policy Implications

Our study suggests that HRQoL interventions should not be one-size-fits-all but rather tailored to the needs of each individual. The identification of distinct HRQoL profiles, such as those seen in this study, presents an opportunity to personalise care strategies and enhance the effectiveness of interventions. For example, those in the low QoL group may benefit from more intensive physical rehabilitation and psychosocial support, whereas those in the high QoL group may require less frequent follow-up and interventions. Implementing personalised care plans, along with routine screening for symptoms of physical deconditioning, nutrition issues, and mental health concerns, can improve the overall experience and help individuals achieve a higher quality of life post-treatment.

Industry Recommendations

Healthcare providers, digital health companies, and insurers can play key roles in improving survivorship care. Industry should invest in tools and services that assess and monitor patients' quality of life in real time, integrate strength and nutrition measures into care platforms, and support personalised intervention pathways. Employers and occupational health programmes should recognise the ongoing impacts of cancer on work ability and wellbeing and offer flexible support for survivors. Developers of patient-reported outcome measures, wearable technologies, and tele-health platforms can further enhance personalised care by helping clinicians track and respond to individual needs throughout recovery and beyond.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG): SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

The Coach Feedback Analysis System: Getting Under the Bonnet of Coach Feedback

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

How coaches provide feedback may impact athlete learning and performance. Research has demonstrated that coaches may lack self-awareness in the types of feedback they provide, by up to 40%. Systematic observation (SO) is a method which identifies coaches' behaviours and has been used extensively in coaching research. SO typically observes a variety of coach behaviours such as instruction, questioning, feedback etc., however tools that help coaches understand their use of specific behaviours (e.g., feedback) may be beneficial. To date no valid and reliable SO tool of coach feedback exists, therefore this research sought to develop a valid and reliable tool that captures specific forms of feedback coaches use.

Research Findings

Following a five-stage validation and reliability procedure including the observation and analysis of hurling, rugby, Australian rules football and soccer coaches, the Coach Feedback Analysis System (CFAS) was developed. The CFAS gives coaches and coach developers the ability to analyse any feedback unit under six categories and eighteen feedback types. These include valence (positive, neutral or negative), information (descriptive or prescriptive), level (self, task, process or self-regulation), autonomy (autonomy supportive, neutral or controlling), audience (full group, small group or individual) and timing (concurrent, post or stopped). Each category and type is included based on a literature review highlighting feedback types shown to impact feedback quality in sport and education.

Policy Implications

The development of the CFAS has important implications for researchers and practitioners alike, allowing the collection of nuanced data on coach feedback. Specifically, given the ability of the CFAS to analyse any feedback unit under six categories and eighteen feedback types, we suggest that this may more easily allow coaches to gauge relationships between feedback types used and athlete outcomes and behaviours. This may be important for coaches as a means of understanding how feedback they provide may be classified and given the established links between certain feedback types with more positive learning and performance outcomes this may help us to understand the possible impact of the feedback coaches use.

Industry Recommendations

We suggest that the CFAS be used as a stimulus for understanding and reflection to support coaches to explore the relationship between their intended and observable use of feedback. This may allow coaches to consider more broadly why they do, what they do, the way that they do it, and what benefit that brings. The CFAS can then be used longitudinally as a means of helping coaches explore whether their intended actions are observable within their practice. Such processes may be of particular benefit to coaches engaged in coach education pathways or as part continuing professional development programmes within sporting organisations.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR code

Stimulating the Senses: How Online Culture and Heritage Events Support Wellbeing for People Living with Dementia

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

People living with dementia (PWD) often face barriers that limit their access to cultural and social activities, especially when travel or in person attendance is difficult. This was highlighted during the Covid-19 pandemic, where online cultural and heritage events emerged as an important way to reduce isolation and support well-being. This research explored how to design online events that are enjoyable, inclusive and genuinely supportive for PWD and their carers. The research aimed to identify what makes online cultural events work well, understand participants' experiences and challenges and develop a framework to guide culture and heritage organisations in creating engaging and accessible online programming.

Research Findings

Online events for PWD provide an opportunity for social interaction and stimulation for individuals. While many people prefer physical events, there is clear evidence that online events can be impactful. In this paper, we co-created a new framework based on the "Six Senses" (continuity, significance, security, belonging, achievement and purpose) which can be utilised to create meaningful online events for PWD. Participants valued sessions that were friendly, interactive and easy to follow. Events worked best when they combined social conversation, short presentations and simple hands-on activities.

Policy Implications

Policymakers should recognise online cultural programming as a meaningful form of social support for PWD. Public bodies and cultural institutions should ensure dementia-inclusive digital access by simplifying booking systems, reducing technical barriers and investing in accessible digital platforms. National dementia strategies can benefit from integrating online cultural participation as part of social prescribing, community engagement and human rights-based care. Sustained funding is needed to support hybrid cultural programmes that reach people in rural areas, people with mobility challenges and those who cannot attend in person. Clear guidance can help organisations adopt dementia-informed design.

Industry Recommendations

Cultural, heritage and arts organisations should design online events that are welcoming, simple to join and centred on familiar, enjoyable experiences. Sessions should follow a clear structure: friendly social chat, a short visual presentation and an easy, hands-on activity. Event hosts should provide digital help in advance, use accessible platforms (e.g., Zoom), send materials beforehand where possible and keep content short and engaging. Marketing must clearly state that events are for people affected by dementia to avoid unintentionally excluding the target audience. By adopting these practices, organisations can create meaningful online cultural experiences that build community and support well-being.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme: Audio-visual / Creative

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): SDG 3: Good Health & Wellbeing

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

Why Coworking Spaces Work, and What Makes People Use Them

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Coworking spaces have expanded rapidly, yet many continue to face low occupancy and uncertain long-term sustainability. Understanding what encourages people to use and remain committed to these spaces is essential for their future viability. This study explores how coworking spaces can be designed and managed to better meet user needs while also supporting local communities. The aim is to identify the factors shaping user buy-in and to develop a practical framework to improve coworking experiences. The objectives are to examine user motivations, evaluate barriers to engagement, and outline actionable strategies that enhance the value and impact of coworking spaces.

Research Findings

The study found that end-user buy-in to coworking spaces is shaped by three interconnected factors: the physical environment, the social dynamic, and opportunities for personal and professional development. Users valued coworking spaces for improved well-being, productivity, and access to suitable workspace infrastructure. However, genuine collaboration was often limited due to functional isolation, the nature of users' work, and insufficient management support. Many spaces played a wider civic role, particularly in rural areas, contributing to local community life. The resulting Value Stack Framework highlights that successful coworking spaces must balance practical facilities, community-building practices, and meaningful learning opportunities to sustain engagement.

Policy Implications

This research highlights the need for policymakers to view coworking spaces not only as economic assets but as vital social infrastructure that supports regional development, community cohesion, and digital inclusion. Funding models should extend beyond initial capital investment to include ongoing support for management roles, programming, and professional development activities that strengthen user engagement. Policies must also address oversupply by aligning new coworking developments with actual local demand. Improved broadband provision, particularly in rural areas, remains essential. Overall, a coordinated national strategy is required to ensure coworking spaces are sustainable, community-centred, and responsive to diverse user needs.

Industry Recommendations

Coworking operators should prioritise high-quality physical environments, ensuring reliable broadband, well-designed work areas, and options for both privacy and collaboration. Investing in active community management is essential, as dedicated managers help foster connection, reduce disruption, and enhance the user experience. Providers should diversify their offerings by integrating training, networking events, and skill-sharing opportunities that add tangible value for users. To remain competitive, operators must adopt flexible business models that respond to changing demand, including hybrid workspace options and tiered pricing. Finally, developing partnerships with local organisations can strengthen the civic role of coworking spaces and stimulate wider community engagement.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme: ICT & ICT Services

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG): SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

From Evidence to Action: Improving Nutrition Support for Cancer Survivors

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Cancer survivorship is increasing globally due to advances in detection and treatment, creating a growing population with complex long-term health needs. Nutrition plays a key role in improving quality of life, reducing recurrence risk and managing comorbidities. However, despite strong evidence linking diet, body composition and metabolic health with survivorship outcomes, access to consistent, evidence-based nutrition care remains limited. This policy brief aims to highlight the gap between evidence and practice in nutrition for cancer survivors, identify key barriers within healthcare systems and propose strategies to integrate nutrition more effectively into survivorship care pathways.

Research Findings

The research highlights that while nutrition significantly influences survivorship outcomes, there is substantial inconsistency in guidance, access and delivery of nutrition care. Survivors frequently experience long-term effects such as fatigue, metabolic dysfunction and cardiovascular risk, which can be improved through appropriate dietary support. However, nutrition is often not systematically embedded within oncology services, and access to dietetic support varies widely. Evidence-based interventions exist but are not consistently implemented, reflecting a clear evidence–practice gap. A tiered model of nutrition care is proposed for integration into current healthcare systems.

Policy Implications

Policymakers should prioritise the integration of nutrition into cancer survivorship care as a standard component of treatment pathways. This includes investing in dietetic workforce capacity, embedding nutrition screening and support across oncology services and ensuring equitable access to evidence-based interventions. Standardised guidelines and care models are needed to reduce variability in practice and improve outcomes. Policy should also support multidisciplinary approaches and long-term follow-up, recognising survivorship as an ongoing phase of care rather than an endpoint. Strengthening health systems to deliver consistent nutrition care could reduce healthcare burden and improve quality of life for survivors.

Industry Recommendations

The National Cancer Control Programme, working with the Health Service Executive, should strengthen the integration of nutrition within cancer survivorship models of care. This includes embedding routine nutrition screening and referral pathways within oncology services, and expanding access to specialist oncology dietitians across acute and community settings. Standardised, evidence-based patient education resources should be developed to support self-management. Investment in digital health and telehealth dietetic services can enhance access and continuity, particularly in underserved areas. A coordinated, multidisciplinary approach is required to ensure consistent implementation of nutrition care across the cancer continuum in Ireland.

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**National Smart Specialisation
Strategy (S3) Theme:**

Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical
Devices

**Sustainable Development Goal
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*The content and views included in this
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Meeting Visitor Needs at Archaeological Sites: Lessons from Ireland's Wild Atlantic Coast

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Understanding visitors is essential for effectively managing sustainable tourism at archaeological sites while safeguarding this fragile and invaluable resource. Effective visitor management strategies can ensure visitors have meaningful and enjoyable experiences while exploring the archaeology without causing damage. This study aims to better understand visitor needs at archaeological sites from their perspective. Visitors to six case study sites along the west coast of Ireland were surveyed via an online questionnaire, with the main goal of identifying the key motivations for visiting archaeological sites, the factors influencing visitor satisfaction, and whether visitors are aware of how to avoid damage.

Research Findings

The findings offer valuable insights into tourists' motivations and satisfaction levels at archaeological sites, emphasising their distinct needs as 'archaeotourists'. Insights from Ireland reveal how visitor characteristics influence motivations that extend beyond the site itself to include the surrounding landscape, which affects emotional experiences and enhances satisfaction levels. The findings also identify a clear link between the availability of onsite interpretive information, satisfaction, and conservation. This study underscores the critical role of informed, visitor-centred management in the strategic management of archaeological sites and contributes to discussions on the sustainable management of archaeotourism and the evolving need to conserve archaeological sites.

Policy Implications

Sustainable archaeological site management should prioritise policies that unify visitor experience and conservation, rather than viewing them as conflicting needs to be balanced. As this study demonstrates, visitors value site conservation and are primarily motivated to engage with the landscape and learn about the past. However, those seeking knowledge often leave dissatisfied. The findings reveal significant gaps in interpretation. Policymakers should invest in accessible, high-quality on-site interpretation and guided tours, with guidelines to maintain authenticity and manage visitor expectations. Additionally, strategic support for infrastructure, pathway design, and conservation awareness is essential for reducing footfall impacts and encouraging sustainable visitor behaviour.

Industry Recommendations

Delivering positive visitor experiences requires addressing motivations influenced by season, visitor type, and group composition. Dissatisfaction among those seeking to learn reveals clear gaps in interpretation and guided services. Site managers should prioritise high-quality, accessible information and extended guided tours to improve learning and emotional engagement. Preserving authenticity is vital for increasing perceived value and satisfaction. Practical improvements—paths, signage, access, facilities, conservation—are essential for managing visitors and protecting the landscape. As archaeological tourism grows and sites risk irreversible loss, fostering understanding, sustainable behaviours, and stakeholder collaboration will support long-term protection and adaptive management.

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

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Audits, Assurance and Absent Workers: An Early Look at Human Rights Reporting Under the CSRD

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Modern slavery remains embedded in global supply chains, and earlier disclosure laws — notably the UK and Australian Modern Slavery Acts — have been criticised for enabling superficial compliance. The EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), transposed into Irish law in 2024, introduces mandatory reporting, third-party assurance, prescriptive standards, and a double materiality assessment. This study asks whether these stronger design features close the gap between corporate human rights policies and actual practice. Drawing on 21 Irish sustainability reports and 32 interviews with sustainability managers, supply chain leads and consultants, it evaluates how firms are implementing human rights due diligence under the new regime.

Research Findings

Disclosure quality has improved, but meaningful practice lags behind policy. While 90% of Irish firms had human rights policies, only 14% reported direct engagement with value chain workers, 24% tracked the effectiveness of their actions, and 29% set related targets. Firms rely heavily on audits, supplier questionnaires and "Speak Up" hotlines as proxies for genuine worker voice, with remediation largely interpreted as supplier termination rather than redress for affected workers. Third-party assurance is the strongest driver of internal change, but the double materiality assessment is vulnerable to internal bias, low supply chain awareness, and steering-group scoring deflation.

Policy Implications

The CSRD advances prior disclosure regimes, particularly through assurance requirements and duty-of-conduct elements. However, three design weaknesses warrant attention. First, the double materiality assessment lets firms deprioritise human rights through proxy stakeholders and discretionary scoring reductions — The European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG) should clarify acceptable practice for auditors. Second, remediation obligations stop short of victim-centred redress, leaving a gap against the UN Guiding Principles. Third, consultants and major audit firms have become de facto standard-setters, raising concentration concerns. Ireland's forthcoming second National Action Plan on Business and Human Rights should address these gaps domestically rather than await further EU action.

Industry Recommendations

Companies preparing for Wave 2 and Wave 3 CSRD reporting should treat human rights due diligence as substantive practice, not a reporting exercise. Four priorities emerge. First, invest in direct worker engagement — audits and supplier surveys are not a substitute for worker voice. Second, move beyond reactive remediation towards grievance mechanisms designed around affected workers' needs and awareness. Third, build internal supply chain visibility before the double materiality assessment, so that steering groups score human rights risks on evidence rather than assumption. Fourth, treat consultant relationships as capability-building partnerships — using their methodological expertise to develop internal knowledge, rather than outsourcing interpretation of material risks entirely.

ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

Fuelling the Distance: Improving Nutrition Practices in Ultra-Endurance Runners

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Ultra-endurance running, also referred to as ultramarathon running or ultrarunning, involves events that exceed marathon distance or last for more than six hours. Events may span single or multiple days and often involve challenging environments and terrain. This places extreme demands on the body, making adequate nutrition critical for supporting performance, recovery, and long-term health. However, many athletes struggle to follow evidence-based nutrition practices. This research aimed to understand how ultra-endurance runners in Ireland make decisions about what, when, and how they eat and hydrate around training and competition. By exploring key factors influencing nutrition behaviours, including knowledge, environment, and motivation, this research identified practical gaps and areas where support is needed.

Research Findings

Qualitative data from ultra-endurance runners indicates that although they are generally aware of the importance of nutrition, this knowledge does not consistently translate into effective behaviours. Many athletes rely on instinct, trial-and-error, or advice from peers rather than qualified nutrition professionals. Time constraints, including work and family commitments, limit their ability to plan meals, often resulting in inconsistent fuelling. Fear of gastrointestinal (gut) issues strongly influences nutrition decisions, leading some to restrict or avoid certain foods based on personal experiences or anecdotal advice. Post-event, many athletes lack a structured approach to support optimal recovery.

Policy Implications

These findings highlight the need to move beyond simply providing nutrition information to these athletes. Policies and programmes should focus on understanding athletes' day-to-day realities to identify how best to apply knowledge in practical ways. Recommendations should be accessible, clear, and evidence-based, while allowing for individual tailoring. There is also a clear need to build trust and engagement with qualified nutrition professionals. Integrating expert guidance into athletic clubs and events could help to bridge the gap between science and practice, promoting safe and effective nutrition strategies and addressing misconceptions around gastrointestinal symptom management.

Industry Recommendations

Sporting organisations and industry stakeholders should provide practical tools for athletes, such as simple fuelling plans, nutrition checklists, and recovery guides. Nutrition education should be delivered through platforms that align with how athletes currently learn, namely through online platforms and peer networks. With regards to managing gastrointestinal symptoms, structured "gut training" can help athletes to build tolerance to foods during exercise, ultimately reducing fear-driven restrictive behaviours and negative performance impacts. Ensuring nutrition strategies are time-efficient and easy to integrate into daily life will be essential for improving adherence, performance, and long-term health outcomes in this growing population.

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Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

Implementing a Virtual Reality Game for Measuring Neck Mobility and Increasing Rehabilitation Compliance

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Neck mobility assessment is important in rehabilitation, but conventional methods may be less engaging and harder to scale for repeated use. This study addresses the need for a low-cost, immersive approach by implementing HeadTurner VR, a virtual reality game designed to measure neck mobility while encouraging rehabilitation compliance. This study aimed to examine whether HeadTurner VR could accurately and reliably measure and record neck movements in an immersive environment. Using 35 participants from a student population, the objectives were to implement the VR exergame, capture a range of neck movements, and evaluate its potential as a practical rehabilitation assessment tool.

Research Findings

This study found that the HeadTurner VR application could measure and record multiple neck rotations in three-dimensional planes in real time using an immersive VR game environment. In a student sample of 35 participants, the recorded neck mobility data showed similarities to values reported in comparable studies using standard cervical measurement devices, supporting the system's initial measurement credibility. The research also reported that the application showed promising early accuracy and reliability as a low-cost, objective tool for neck rehabilitation assessment. At the same time, it identified that further analysis is needed, particularly to examine how factors such as gender, age, and weight may influence neck range of motion and system performance.

Policy Implications

Policies for musculoskeletal rehabilitation could support the use of validated, low-cost VR tools such as HeadTurner VR for home and community assessment, as the study identifies a need for portable systems that improve monitoring, motivation, and exercise compliance in neck rehabilitation. Health services should also require clear validation, procurement, and clinical governance standards before routine adoption, since the findings report promising early accuracy and reliability, but note that further testing is still needed across demographics such as age, gender, and weight.

Industry Recommendations

Industry should prioritise low-cost, portable VR rehabilitation tools that combine accurate movement tracking with engaging game design, as HeadTurner VR was developed to support both neck mobility assessment and rehabilitation compliance and showed promising early accuracy, reliability, and low simulator sickness. Companies should also build in accessibility, inclusive design, and early clinical validation so products are usable across diverse patient groups and suitable for wider implementation.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG): SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being

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The content and views included in this policy brief are based on independent, peer-reviewed research and do not necessarily reflect the position of RISE@ATU.

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A Novel 3D Printed Portable Device for Environmental Monitoring

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

This publication proposes a low-cost, solar-powered portable potentiostat designed to enable on-site environmental monitoring, particularly in resource-limited settings. Its main aim is to improve accessibility of electrochemical sensing by removing reliance on grid power and bulky lab equipment. The objectives include developing a compact, energy-efficient device, validating its performance against standard laboratory potentiostats, and demonstrating its application in detecting environmental contaminants, such as pollutants in water. Overall, this work seeks to support real-time, field-based analysis while promoting sustainable and decentralised monitoring solutions.

Research Findings

This study finds that the solar-powered portable potentiostat delivers reliable electrochemical measurements comparable to standard laboratory systems while operating independently of grid electricity. Field tests show it can accurately detect environmental contaminants, such as pollutants in water, in real time. A key feature is its integration with low-cost, 3D-printed sensor components, which enable rapid prototyping, local production, and easy customisation for different applications without sacrificing performance or reproducibility. Together, the portability, renewable energy use, and additive manufacturing approach make the system well suited to scalable, accessible, and sustainable environmental monitoring in resource-limited settings.

Policy Implications

This research has important policy implications for expanding environmental monitoring in low-resource and remote settings. The use of solar power and low-cost 3D-printed components supports decentralised, sustainable monitoring systems that reduce reliance on expensive laboratory infrastructure and stable grid electricity. Policymakers could leverage this technology to strengthen water quality surveillance, improve early detection of pollutants, and support environmental regulation in underserved regions. It also highlights the value of investing in open, locally manufacturable scientific tools to increase resilience, reduce costs, and improve data-driven environmental decision-making.

Industry Recommendations

The study suggests several opportunities for industry adoption, particularly in environmental sensing, water quality monitoring, and low-cost analytical device manufacturing. Companies could integrate solar-powered potentiostats and 3D-printed sensor components into portable testing kits for field technicians and decentralised monitoring networks. The use of additive manufacturing enables rapid customisation and scalable production, reducing development and deployment costs. Industry stakeholders are encouraged to collaborate with research institutions to refine device robustness, standardise performance across applications, and support commercialisation pathways that prioritise affordability, sustainability, and accessibility in global environmental monitoring markets.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Renewable Energy, Climate
Change & Sustainability

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

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McDonagh, P., Shanks, K., Ralphs, K., Skillen, N. & McCrudden, D. (2026). From commercial photocatalysts to concentrated solar systems: mechanistic elucidation of cellulose depolymerisation. *Journal of Physics: Energy* 8(2), 025006.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7655/ae5f44>

National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Renewable Energy, Climate Change & Sustainability

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Shining a Light on Cellulose: From Waste to Worth

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Biomass is an abundant renewable carbon source, yet it remains under-exploited due to the energy-intensive and costly nature of traditional conversion. Central to this challenge is cellulose, its primary component. Unlocking its chemical value may be key to decarbonising fuels and chemical manufacturing, but success hinges on mastering the complex depolymerisation process. Photocatalysis offers a sustainable pathway to break down these polymer chains under mild low-carbon conditions. To move from lab concepts to deployable systems, we must prioritise understanding the mechanisms of the depolymerisation process. By combining these mechanistic insights with scalable, solar-driven technologies, we can deliver a tangible impact on the global bioeconomy.

Research Findings

This study utilised di- to tetra-saccharide model systems to identify the mechanism of photocatalytic depolymerisation of cellulose using commercial catalysts. Findings revealed that Zinc Oxide (ZnO) provided significantly higher glucose selectivity; however, efficiency declined as chain length increased. This represents a critical hurdle for real-world feedstocks, necessitating rigorous benchmarking of photocatalysts to ensure commercial viability. By identifying the pivotal role of photogenerated holes and reactive oxygen species, this work determined the depolymerisation pathway and associated oxidation mechanisms. Moreover, the study demonstrated that concentrated solar irradiation effectively activated ZnO, overcoming the low proportion of UV light in the solar spectrum.

Policy Implications

Current policy demonstrates growing recognition of the bioeconomy yet support for emerging conversion technologies such as photocatalysis is still developing. The findings on the efficiency hurdles suggest that prioritising standardised benchmarking is essential to inform investment and guide technological development. Such benchmarking must be integrated with system-level considerations, including reactor design and scale-up, to ensure future deployment. Increased support for pilot-scale demonstration and integrated solar-driven systems is required to validate performance under practical conditions. Ultimately, a balanced policy approach supporting rigorous benchmarking and system integration is vital for advancing solar-driven biomass conversion toward commercial deployment.

Industry Recommendations

To bridge the gap between lab-scale innovation and commercial application, industry requires robust policy roadmaps. Specifically, technologies like photocatalysis need clear pathways through Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) to ensure market integration. Rather than focusing solely on catalyst design, attention should be given to deployable, system-level solutions using commercially available materials. Progress requires coordinated advances in reactor engineering, light management, and integration with existing solar and biorefinery infrastructure. In parallel, improved utilisation of the full solar spectrum, including strategies to redirect underused light into complementary applications, will enhance overall efficiency and economic feasibility, supporting the low-carbon transition.

Strengthening Sustainability Education for Future Food Systems

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

The transition towards sustainable food systems is critical for addressing global challenges, including climate change, biodiversity loss and food insecurity. Recognising the role of education in preparing graduates to address interconnected sustainability challenges, this study examined how nutrition and agri-food educators understand, teach, and integrate food sustainability concepts into curricula. The study explored the knowledge, perceptions, and teaching practices of educators participating in the Erasmus+ Train to Sustain project across Ireland, Italy, Poland, and Slovenia. By identifying strengths, gaps, and barriers in sustainability education, the study sought to inform curriculum reform and support more comprehensive and interdisciplinary approaches to sustainability teaching.

Research Findings

The findings demonstrated strong recognition among nutrition and agri-food educators of the importance of embedding sustainability within education. Educators showed strongest awareness of environmental and social sustainability issues, particularly food waste reduction, ethical consumption, local food systems, and resource management. Experiential learning approaches were commonly used to engage learners with sustainability concepts. However, the study identified more limited understanding of economic sustainability, cultural dimensions, and whole food systems thinking. Participants also highlighted the need for additional professional development, practical teaching resources, and interdisciplinary curriculum approaches to strengthen sustainability education and better prepare graduates.

Policy Implications

The findings highlight important policy implications for sustainability education within the agri-food and nutrition sectors. Greater integration of food sustainability across curricula may be supported through interdisciplinary and systems-based approaches aligned with UNESCO sustainability education frameworks and relevant Sustainable Development Goals. The study also demonstrates the need for continuous professional development to improve educators' understanding of economic and cultural dimensions of sustainability. Investment in accessible teaching resources, digital learning tools, and experiential learning opportunities is needed to support curriculum delivery. Monitoring and evaluation frameworks are also needed to assess how sustainability education develops student competencies.

Industry Recommendations

The findings highlight opportunities for industry stakeholders to support curriculum development through partnerships that provide real-world learning opportunities, including farm visits, case studies, placements, and guest expert contributions. Greater engagement with educators could also improve understanding of economic sustainability, food system resilience, fair trade, and sustainable supply chains. The findings further suggest a need for industry-led training and knowledge exchange on emerging practices such as circular agriculture, resource-efficient technologies, and sustainable production methods to help equip graduates with the practical sustainability skills and systems-thinking required to meet evolving workforce and food system challenges.

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**National Smart Specialisation
Strategy (S3) Theme:** AgriFood &
AgriTech

**Sustainable Development Goal
(SDG):** SDG 12: Responsible
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the ERDF Northern & Western Regional
Programme 2021-2027.

Supporting Elite Gaelic Games Student-Athletes in Higher Education

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Elite Gaelic games student-athletes (EGSAs) inter-county players simultaneously enrolled in full-time higher education face unique dual-career pressures. Unlike professional pathway athletes, EGSAs receive no financial remuneration yet compete at professional performance standards, while managing full academic workloads without a centralised institutional support system. This research examined the most significant perceived barriers to balancing sport and study among EGSAs, identified the key predictors of dual-career strain, and generated evidence to inform policy and practice in both sport and higher education.

Research Findings

A cross-sectional survey of 320 elite Gaelic games student-athletes identified three major barriers to balancing sport and study: institutional, time and geographical constraints. Institutional rigidity, including inflexible academic scheduling, limited lecturer awareness and poor coordination between sport and education systems, was the strongest predictor of strain. Higher training loads increased time pressure, although athletes completing shorter, more structured sessions reported lower strain. Travel between university, home and training venues affected 45% of participants, adding further burden to already demanding schedules. Coping capacity emerged as the strongest protective factor, with athletes better able to manage competing demands reporting substantially lower levels of strain across all barrier domains.

Policy Implications

These barriers are structural, not individual - they are produced by systems not designed for the dual-career athlete. Addressing them requires coordinated action between higher education institutions, national governing bodies, and government. These findings also suggest that coping capacity is the single most powerful modifiable resource available to athletes navigating these conditions. Developing coping and self-regulation skills through embedded psychoeducational programmes should therefore be a priority alongside structural reform, not as a substitute for it, but as a parallel investment in athletes' ability to manage demands that no institutional redesign will fully eliminate.

Industry Recommendations

Higher education institutions and national governing bodies should implement coordinated dual-career support frameworks for elite Gaelic games student-athletes, including flexible academic scheduling, improved lecturer awareness, athlete welfare supports, and training and competition structures that avoid overlap with examinations and college competitions. The proposed 2027 GAA/LGFA/Camogie merger should embed dual-career athlete welfare as a core governance priority, with standardised supports implemented consistently across all codes.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme: Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG): SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

Trustworthy Generative AI for Smarter Decision-making and Sustainable Farming

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Modern smart farming systems increasingly rely on Artificial Intelligence (AI) to automate monitoring, climate control and crop management. However, agricultural AI systems often face two major challenges: limited high-quality farming data for diverse scenarios and lack of transparency in AI-driven decisions. This research aimed to develop an explainable AI framework capable of generating realistic synthetic farming data while also improving trust in automated decision-support systems. The study introduced a novel Conditional Time-Transformer model that generates context-aware greenhouse data using environmental conditions such as weather, time patterns and operational settings, while integrating explainable AI methods to assess how AI systems make decisions.

Research Findings

The proposed AI framework improved the quality and realism of synthetic greenhouse data compared to existing generative AI approaches. The model achieved stronger alignment with real-world greenhouse conditions and improved downstream decision-making performance for greenhouse control tasks. Importantly, the research demonstrated that explainable AI techniques can help evaluate whether AI systems trained on synthetic data make decisions in ways that remain consistent with real farming behaviour. The findings showed that combining conditional generative AI with explainability can support more transparent, reliable and trustworthy smart farming systems while reducing dependence on expensive long-term agricultural data collection.

Policy Implications

The findings highlight the need for governance frameworks that promote transparency and accountability in AI-driven agricultural technologies. Policymakers should encourage the use of explainable AI validation methods before deploying AI systems in high-impact farming operations. The research also supports public investment in trustworthy AI infrastructure for agriculture, particularly for climate-smart and resource-efficient farming systems. Synthetic data generation may help overcome agricultural data shortages while preserving operational privacy and reducing deployment costs. However, regulatory guidelines should require ongoing validation of AI reasoning and decision consistency to ensure safe and reliable adoption within real-world agricultural environments.

Industry Recommendations

Agricultural technology providers and greenhouse operators should integrate explainable AI tools into smart farming platforms to improve transparency and farmer trust. Companies deploying AI-based greenhouse automation should validate AI decisions using both performance metrics and explainability assessments before operational use. The use of synthetic data generation can help organisations train AI systems under rare or extreme environmental conditions without waiting for long-term field data collection. Industry stakeholders should also prioritise human-in-the-loop monitoring for AI-assisted climate-control decisions, particularly in safety-critical situations where incorrect predictions could affect crop productivity, resource usage or operational stability.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme: AgriFood & AgriTech

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG): SDG 2: Zero Hunger

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ATU Policy Brief Series QR Code

The Anxiolytic Effects of an Acute Bout of Resistance Exercise in Young Women

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Generalized anxiety disorder is a common debilitating chronic condition, with women twice as likely to experience in their lifetime. Frontline treatments such as SSRIs (Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors) and CBT (Cognitive Behavioural Therapy) are often costly, inaccessible, with some reporting negative side effects. Resistance exercise is emerging as a potentially beneficial, low-cost, easily accessible treatment option. Resistance exercise training has a myriad of physical health benefits but less is known about its acute psychological impact. This study examined the effects of moderate-to-high intensity resistance exercise compared to low-intensity on state anxiety in young women with analogue generalized anxiety disorder.

Research Findings

Both moderate-to-high and low-intensity resistance exercise produced significant reductions in state anxiety and feelings of tension in young women with analogue generalised anxiety disorder, with no meaningful difference between intensities. Notably, even the low-intensity sham condition (just 20% of est 1RM – one repetition maximum) yielded large anxiolytic effects, suggesting the benefits may begin at very light loads. Crucially, these psychological improvements were independent of participants' expectations, suggesting that the effects were driven by the exercise itself rather than any placebo influence.

Policy Implications

Resistance exercise should be formally integrated into acute anxiety management guidelines for young women, with explicit acknowledgement that low-intensity is as effective as moderate-to-high intensity for beginners. Current physical activity recommendations focused on aerobic exercise should be broadened to include more specific resistance-exercise recommendations. Healthcare practitioners and mental health professionals should consider resistance exercise as a low-barrier, accessible intervention for acute anxiety management. Community fitness facilities and student health services should offer entry-level resistance exercise programmes specifically targeting anxious populations.

Industry Recommendations

Exercise practitioners for mental health should be considered as part of multi-disciplinary care teams in the treatment of anxiety disorders. Fitness industry professionals, including personal trainers and gym instructors, should design beginner-friendly resistance exercise programmes using light loads, removing the intimidation barrier that often deters anxious individuals from engaging.

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme: Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices
Sustainable Development Goal (SDG): SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being

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Gender Disparities Among Elite Gaelic Games Student-Athletes in Higher Education

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Male and female inter-county Gaelic games athletes compete within the same amateur framework of high performance. Yet the conditions of their participation are not equal. Female athletes consistently access fewer resources, receive less financial reimbursement, and are afforded lower institutional recognition than male counterparts despite facing equivalent demands. This research explored how gender shapes the dual-career experiences of elite Gaelic games student-athletes (EGSAs) enrolled in full-time higher education in Ireland, examining how structural inequalities in facilities, finance, and institutional support are experienced in daily dual-career life.

Research Findings

Reflexive thematic analysis of four gender-segregated focus groups (N=14; 7 male, 7 female) identified three interconnected themes shaping the dual-career experiences of elite Gaelic games student-athletes. Female athletes reported unequal access to training facilities, resources and financial supports, often self-funding equipment and supplements provided to male counterparts. Women also prioritised education more frequently when academic and sporting demands conflicted, reflecting concerns around long-term financial security. Significant disparities in financial reimbursement were identified, with female participants capped at €290 from the LGFA over six months of travel, while male players in the same county received mileage rates per kilometre. Several participants reported considering leaving inter-county sport due to the personal financial burden involved.

Policy Implications

These findings reveal what this research terms 'gendered amateurism' - an amateur system that demands equivalent commitment from all athletes while distributing resources and recognition unevenly along gender lines. The proposed 2027 merger of the GAA, LGFA, and Camogie Association is the most significant governance opportunity in a generation to address these inequities, but structural integration must be accompanied by cultural change.

Industry Recommendations

The merged governing body should establish transparent, equitable expense reimbursement policies applied consistently across all codes and genders. Minimum facility access standards should be implemented at county board level to ensure women's teams have consistent training environments independent of men's programme availability. Higher education institutions should proactively recognise elite female athletes, particularly camogie and ladies' football players, within dual-career and scholarship frameworks. The Female Player Charter introduced by the GAA in 2023 should also be implemented with clear accountability mechanisms and publicly reported at both county and national level.

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Further Reading:

Whelan, C., Ryan, L., Gomez, J., & Daly, E. (2026) A reflexive thematic analysis exploring gender disparities among elite Gaelic games student-athletes at third-level education in Ireland, *Journal for the Study of Sports and Athletes in Education*, 1–22. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19357397.2026.2668990>

National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme: Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG): SDG 5: Gender Equality

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Looking Ahead: Supporting Research Visibility, Engagement and Impact at ATU

The ATU Research Coordinator Team would like to sincerely thank all researchers who contributed to the inaugural ATU Research-Informed, Industry-Linked Policy Brief Series (2025/2026). The strong level of engagement from researchers across ATU's departments, faculties and campuses has played a central role in shaping and strengthening this initiative during its first year.

This series has been developed under the RISE@ATU programme as part of a broader institutional commitment to supporting research visibility, knowledge mobilisation, structured external engagement and evidence-informed impact across Atlantic Technological University. By translating peer-reviewed research into accessible, outward-facing and policy-relevant outputs, the series aims to strengthen connections between research, policy, industry, practice and wider society, while supporting regional innovation and strategic development priorities.

All policy briefs published as part of this initiative are openly accessible through the European Commission-supported Zenodo platform, where each brief is assigned a unique DOI to support measurable visibility, dissemination, discoverability and long-term accessibility.

ATU Policy Brief Series – Zenodo Channel QR Code

(Link: [ATU Policy Brief Series – Zenodo Channel](#))

The ATU Policy Brief Series will continue to evolve as a platform for supporting accessible, publicly engaged and impact-oriented research communication across the university. As the series continues to develop, the ATU Research Coordinator Team welcomes future submissions from researchers across all ATU faculties and campuses. We particularly encourage contributions that demonstrate clear societal, policy, industry or community relevance, and which align with regional, national and international priorities, including Ireland's Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) themes and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Researchers interested in contributing to future editions of the ATU Research-Informed, Industry-Linked Policy Brief Series are encouraged to contact the ATU Research Coordinator Team.

ATU Policy Brief Series - Submission Form QR Code

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The Higher Education Authority

The policy briefs included within this publication are based on peer-reviewed journal articles authored by researchers affiliated with Atlantic Technological University (ATU). Each brief was prepared in collaboration with contributing authors and formatted for accessibility and policy-facing dissemination purposes. Minor editorial adjustments were made where necessary for formatting, accessibility and consistency purposes.

All policy briefs published as part of this initiative are openly accessible through Zenodo, the European Commission-supported open research repository designed to support the long-term preservation, discoverability and dissemination of research outputs. Each policy brief is assigned an individual Digital Object Identifier (DOI), supporting formal citation, measurable visibility and long-term accessibility.

The ATU Research-Informed, Industry-Linked Policy Brief Series forms part of a broader institutional emphasis under the RISE@ATU programme on research impact, knowledge mobilisation and strategic research communication, particularly in relation to supporting accessible, publicly engaged and policy-facing dissemination of research outputs.

Views expressed within individual policy briefs are those of the respective authors and do not necessarily reflect the official views of Atlantic Technological University or associated funding bodies.

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Northern & Western
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HEA

An tÚdarás um Ard-Oideachas
The Higher Education Authority

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ATU

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